

MONITORING DAMAGE IN BONDED COMPOSITE REPAIRS OF CRACKED METALLIC COMPONENTS USING SURFACE STRAIN MEASUREMENTS

Stephen C. Galea

*Airframes and Engines Division, Defence Science and Technology Organisation,
Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory, 506 Lorimer Street, Fishermens Bend,
Victoria, 3207, Australia.*

SUMMARY: Adhesively bonded fibre reinforced composite patches have been used extensively, over the last two decades, on Royal Australian Air Force (RAAF) aircraft to repair fatigue-cracked metallic aircraft components. The bonded repair to the cracked structure - crack patching - allows the restoration of strength and stiffness of the structure, as well as slowing crack growth by reducing stress intensity. However, especially for critical components with bonded repairs, the crack needs to be inspected at specific intervals in order to monitor crack growth and thus ensure structural integrity is not compromised. This paper reports on an in-situ health monitoring technique of a crack-patched component based on surface strains on the patch to detect and monitor fatigue cracks in the metallic component. Surface mounted electrical resistance strain gauges were installed on the patch of crack-patched specimens. The specimen was then subjected to constant amplitude tension-dominated cyclic loading. Crack lengths, using eddy-current NDI, and surface strain measurements were monitored with increasing number of load cycles. The full field surface stresses were also determined by using a thermoelastic technique. These results were compared with the surface strain gauge measurements. The results showed that the surface strain measurements on the patch commence to deviate, from far-field values, at about 7-8 mm ahead of the crack. Surface strains on the patch in the vicinity of the crack appear to vary linearly with increasing crack length. Also significant variations in residual strains were observed with increasing crack length. These results indicate that monitoring surface strains, and residual surface strains, appear to be a promising technique for detecting and monitoring crack growth beneath composite patches.

KEYWORDS: bonded composite repairs, bonded repairs, bonded composite patches

INTRODUCTION

For economic reasons there is a current trend to operate military aircraft well past their original design life. However, this results in a rapidly increasing number of airframe corrosion and cracking problems and gives rise to the urgent need for cost-effective, efficient repair procedures. This situation is extremely relevant to the Royal Australian Air Force (RAAF) where many aircraft types, such as the F-111, P3C, Macchi will have exceeded their design life well before they can be replaced.

The application of bonded composite patches to repair or reinforce defective metallic structures is becoming recognised as a very effective versatile procedure for many types of

problems. Immediate applications of bonded patches are in the fields of repair of cracking, localised reinforcement after removal of corrosion damage and for reduction of fatigue strain. Adhesively bonded fibre reinforced composite patches have recently been used on the primary structure to repair cracking in the lower wing skin of the F-111C. The bonded repair to the cracked structure - crack patching - allows the restoration of strength and stiffness of the structure, as well as slowing crack growth by reducing stress intensity.

However, especially for critical components with bonded repairs, the crack needs to be inspected at specific intervals in order to monitor crack growth and thus ensure structural integrity is not compromised. Therefore, current studies are focused on the assessment of new techniques in order to achieve in-situ real-time measurement of patch integrity and effectiveness. This application would allow the operator to move away from current costly time-based maintenance procedures toward real-time health condition monitoring of the bonded repair and the repaired structure. These systems would allow timely decisions on preventative and scheduled maintenance before failure of the repair or repaired structure.

This paper reports on an in-situ health monitoring technique of a crack-patched component based on surface strains on the patch to detect and monitor fatigue cracks in the metallic component. Both the surface strains under load and the relative change in residual surface strains were monitored as the crack length increased. The full field surface stresses were also determined by using a thermoelastic technique. These results were compared with the surface strain gauge measurements. The results showed that the surface strain measurements on the patch do vary substantially as the crack passes beneath the strain gauge. Variations in strains were observed 7-8 mm ahead of the crack. Also significant variations in residual strains were observed with increasing crack length. These results indicate that monitoring surface strains, and residual surface strains, appears to be a promising technique for detecting and monitoring crack growth beneath composite repairs.

SPECIMEN

The experimental program was conducted on 2024 T3 specimens 3.14 mm thick having starting cracks with crack length, a , of about 10 mm repaired with unidirectional boron/epoxy 7 ply (0.9 mm) thick semicircular patches. A layer of FM 73 film adhesive was cocured onto the boron/epoxy bonding surface. The patches were then bonded with adhesive FM 73 at 120°C, following surface treatment of the metal using the silane process and the boron/epoxy patches by blasting with alumina grit on the cocured adhesive layer.

The aluminium skins were tested in a back-to-back honeycomb sandwich arrangement by bonding each skin onto aluminium honeycomb as shown in Fig. 1a). This arrangement was used for two reasons:

1. Fabrication considerations, i.e. the skin/patch configuration is unsymmetric therefore the coefficient of thermal expansion (cte) mismatch between the boron patch and the aluminium will cause the panel to bend considerably after the patch has been cured onto the metal skin. Thus by undertaking both processes, i.e. co-curing the patch onto the skin and bonding the skin onto the honeycomb, simultaneously the resultant curvature due to thermal mismatch will be minimised.

2. To minimise the global secondary bending of the panels during testing, due to load path eccentricity in each skin/patch configuration. That is, the bending moments arise from the shift of the neutral axis by the patch. The resistance to bending resulting from the honeycomb support is considered to be a reasonable simulation of the support that would be provided by typical military aircraft structure.

Fig. 1: Schematic of the specimen used for this experimental program.

SENSOR LOCATIONS

In order to study the surface strain behaviour of the patch as the crack grows strain gauges were attached as shown in Fig. 2. Two far-field strain gauges were located on each side of the specimen, these were denoted as 4S1 and 4S2 - far-field gauges on the patch for sides 1 and 2, respectively, and 5S1 and 5S2 - far-field gauges on the aluminium skin for sides 1 and 2, respectively (see Fig. 2). Note that side 1 denotes the side with the strip strain gauges and the sensing direction of all strain gauges was in the loading, y , direction of the specimen.

The strip gauges were attached at three x stations along the crack centreline. The centreline of each strip of gauges was aligned perpendicular to the crack centreline. The first strip, denoted as strip 1, consisted of column of 10 strain gauges and was located 32 mm ($x = 32$) from the specimen edge and approximately 22 mm ahead of the crack tip, as shown in Fig. 2. The individual gauges are denoted as 1a - 1j with the 5th gauge, 1e, positioned over the crack centreline. These gauges consisted of a sensing length of 1 mm with a pitch of 2 mm. The second strip, strip 2 with gauges 2a - 2e, consisted of a strip of five gauges located 20 mm from the specimen edge ($x = 20$) and approximately 10 mm ahead of the crack tip, as shown in Fig. 2. These gauges consisted of a gauge length of 2 mm with a pitch of 3 mm with the 3rd gauge, 2c, positioned over the crack centreline. The third strip, strip 3 with gauges 3a - 3e, was similar to strip 2 and was located 5 mm ($x = 5$) from the specimen edge and approximately 5 mm behind the crack tip, as shown in Fig. 2. The 3rd gauge, 3c, was positioned over the crack centreline.

Table 1: Description of the applied stresses and loads for each load case.

Load Condition		1	2	3	4
Nominal stress, σ (MPa)	Max, σ_{\max}	120.0	135.0	154.0	180.0
	Min, σ_{\min}	12.0	27.0	46.2	72.0
Stress ratio, R ($\sigma_{\min} / \sigma_{\max}$)		0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4
Applied load, P (kN)	Max, P_{\max}	122.0	136.0	156.0	184.0
	Min, P_{\min}	13.0	28.0	47.0	73.0

At every 10000 cycles the cyclic loading was interrupted to undertake strain surveys and crack length measurements. The crack length, a , was measured using an eddy-current surface probe which enabled measurement of the crack length to within an accuracy of about ± 0.5 mm. The strain gauge and load data were recorded using PC-based data acquisition systems. The strain survey was taken during load holds, at every 10 kN, when loading the specimen from 0 to 70 kN at a loading rate of 1 kN/sec. The strain measurements were also taken during the downloading from 70 to 0 kN at every 10 kN increments. Strain gauges were calibrated and zeroed, once only, at the start of the study, i.e. $N = 0$ cycles.

Thermoelastic Analysis

Thermoelastic scans of the patch, for various specimens, using the FAST, Focal-plane Array for Synchronous Thermography, system Ryall and Wong were also undertaken. Provided that adiabatic conditions are maintained it is possible to show that the change in temperature and stress are directly proportional, i.e.

$$-\rho c_{\epsilon} \frac{\Delta T}{T_0} = (\alpha_{11} \Delta \sigma_{11} + \alpha_{22} \Delta \sigma_{22})$$

where ΔT is the local cyclic change in temperature, T_0 is the local absolute temperature, ρ is the density, α_{ii} is the coefficient of thermal expansion, c_{ϵ} is the specific heat at constant strain and $\Delta \sigma_{ii}$ is the cyclic principal stress amplitude. The subscripts 1 and 2 denote directions parallel and perpendicular to the fibre. FAST measures the temperature changes of the coupon under cyclic loading using an infra-red technique and the resultant thermal image effectively represents the stress distribution in the component. For specimens with unidirectional patches, as is the case here, stresses on the surface of the patch are predominantly in the fibre direction, therefore the FAST scan basically represents the σ_{11} surface stress distribution. Specimen 1, with a 45 mm long crack, and a specimen with a 10 mm long crack were scanned using FAST under the load conditions 35 ± 25 kN at 8 Hz.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 3: Plot of crack length with increasing number of loading cycles.

Fig. 3 shows the measured crack growth against number of applied cycles for Spec1. This figure also illustrates the number of cycles, N, applied during each load condition.

Fig. 4: Variation of strain distributions normal to the crack with increasing crack length for (a) strip 1, $x = 32$ and (b) strip 3, $x = 5$ at 70 kN (ϵ_{70}) load.

Fig. 5: FAST thermoelastic scans of (a) Spec1, side 1 with $a = 45$ mm, and (b) a specimen with 10 mm long crack, taken under the loading conditions of 35 ± 25 kN at 8 Hz.

Fig. 4 shows the strain distributions at 70 kN load, along a line perpendicular to the crack centreline, at $x = 32$ and 5 , i.e. for strips 1 and 3, respectively. Note that, all the 70 kN load strain data presented in this report has been adjusted such that all strains at zero load were set to zero, i.e. the residual strains were set to zero for all the strain at load cases. This figure illustrates (1) the variation of strain across the crack, and (2) the variation in the strain distribution with increasing crack length. These figures show that the maximum strains do not occur over the crack and are consistent with the FAST scans undertaken on this specimen, Spec 1 with the crack length at 45 mm, and to a lesser extent on a specimen with a 10 mm long crack, see Fig. 5a) and b), respectively. Fig. 5a) shows quite distinctively, a long narrow region of low stresses directly over the crack and regions of high stress above and below the crack. These results are consistent with work undertaken on similar patched cracked specimens [5] and patched cracked specimens with 12 mm thick aluminium cracked skins [4]. Vertical line scans, taken from the scan for Spec1 shown in Fig. 5a), at various positions along the crack are illustrated in Fig. 6. These vertical scans show similar distributions as the strain distributions in Fig. 4. This effect is due to the adhesive shear lag and the local secondary bending. The secondary bending is caused from the load path eccentricity as the load passes through the patch over the crack; the severity of secondary bending will depend on the amount of load path deviation required and the out-of-plane flexibility of the honeycomb core. These regions of high and low stresses become more pronounced, i.e. peaks increase and troughs decrease, as the crack increases in length and the load carried by the patch increases. Note also that the trough appears to be reasonably sharp in nature, however the peaks tend to be broad, see Figs. 4 and 6.

Fig. 6: Vertical line scans from FAST thermoelastic scan of Spec1, side 1 with $a = 45$ mm, taken under the loading conditions of 35 ± 25 kN at 8 Hz.

The strain readings taken at strip 1, Fig. 4a), indicate that the crack has veered about 2 mm upward, from the initial crack centreline, as it passes this strip gauge. This is also illustrated in the FAST scans of Fig. 5 and 6. In fact the vertical line scans show that the location of the minimum strains (ϵ^{\min}) are quite sharp and appear to indicate precisely the location of the crack, whereas the maximum strain peaks are broad plateaus of high strains (ϵ^{\max}). These plateaus have a centre located between 6 - 8 mm above and below the crack and widths between 4 - 8 mm wide. Thus when attempting to detect and monitor the minimum strains, which appear to occur over the crack, then the position of the sensor is critical. However in order to detect and monitor maximum strains the positioning of the sensor appears to be less sensitive to location.

The strain gauges at strip 1, $x = 32$, start to detect the crack when the sensors are approximately 7-8 mm upstream of the crack. That is to say the region of influence of the crack extends to about 7-8 mm ahead of the tip. The extent of this region will be specimen dependent and will depend on factors such as adhesive shear lag and local secondary bending; i.e. on the stiffness of the adhesive, adherands and the honeycomb core.

The measured strains at zero load, ϵ_0 , (residual strains) are shown in Figs. 7a) and 7b) for strips 1 and 3, respectively. These strains are not the true residual strains, since they do not contain the component of residual (thermal) strains due to bonding of the patch onto the aluminium skin. That is, these measurements are basically changes in residual strains in the patch as the crack propagates. This phenomenon is believed to be due to the redistribution of residual thermal strains as the crack propagates under the patch - hence these effects are limited to the immediate vicinity around the crack and are similar to the redistribution of residual thermal stresses experienced in composite laminates after impact has occurred. Fig. 7 shows (1) the spatial variation of residual strain distributions perpendicular to the crack and (2) the variation of residual strain distributions with increasing crack length at stations $x = 32$ and 5. The strain distributions at the two x stations show a surprisingly large change in residual strain with increasing crack length. For strip 1, $x = 32$, the residual strain over the crack drops to $-400 \mu\epsilon$ and the strains above and below the crack increase to $400 \mu\epsilon$ as the crack passes under the strip. Once again changes in residual strains due to the crack appear to occur at about 7-8 mm ahead of the crack. This appears consistent with the strains observed when the specimen is subjected to load, see Fig. 4. The overall features of the residual strain distributions at the two x stations are similar to the strain distributions measured under load.

For the strains measured at strip 1 and 3 variations of the maximum (ϵ^{\max} taken from gauges 1i and 3e) and minimum (ϵ^{\min} taken from gauges 1d and 3c) strains with increasing crack length are illustrated in Figs. 8a) and 8b), respectively. This figure also shows the variations in strains for the two load conditions 0 and 70 kN, ϵ_0 and ϵ_{70} , respectively and illustrates quite clearly the sensitivity of strains to crack length. Fig. 8a) shows once again that the region of influence of the crack extends for about 7-8 mm ahead of the crack tip. Also there appears to be a linear variation in ϵ^{\max} and ϵ^{\min} , for both the residual strains and the 70 kN load case, with crack length for strip 1 once the crack has been detected, i.e. for $a > 25$ mm. Similar results were found by Chang and Sirkis where a linear relationship between strain, in the patch over the crack, and crack length was observed. Fig. 8 also shows that the residual strains have a greater sensitivity to changes in crack length than strain changes measured under load. Therefore it seems that the measurement of residual strains may be a sensitive method for detecting and monitoring crack growth.

Percentage changes in ϵ^{\max} (gauges 1i, 2e, 3e) and ϵ^{\min} (gauges 1d and 3c), compared to far-field measurements, $\epsilon_{70}^{\text{ff}}$ taken from gauge 4S1 at 70 kN load, are then plotted in Fig. 9a) against $a-x_s$. Fig. 9b) shows the variation of the parameter $(\epsilon^{\max} - \epsilon^{\min})/\epsilon_{70}^{\text{ff}}$ with $a-x_s$ for the residual and 70 kN load conditions. The parameter, $a-x_s$, allows the observation of variations in strain from the frame of reference of the sensor where x_s is the x position of the sensor and a is the crack length. Hence negative values, of $a-x_s$, indicate the sensor is upstream of the crack tip and positive values indicate that the crack has passed the sensor and the sensor is downstream of the crack tip. The first figure shows the general linear variation in ϵ^{\max} and ϵ^{\min} with crack growth for the crack upstream and downstream of the sensor. However for conditions where the crack tip has progressed more than 30 mm past the sensor, both the

Fig. 7: Variation of strain distributions normal to the crack with increasing crack length for (a) strip 1, $x = 32$ and (b) strip 3, $x = 5$ at 0 kN (ϵ_0) load.

Fig. 8: Variation of maximum and minimum strains with increasing crack length for the two load conditions 0 and 70 kN, ϵ_0 and ϵ_{70} , for (a) strip 1, gauge 1i and 1d, and (b) strip 3, gauges 3e and 3c, respectively. The far-field strains are taken from gauge 4S1.

Fig. 9: (a) Percentage variation of maximum and minimum strain with increasing crack length, at 70 kN (ϵ_{70}), for gauges 1i, 2e, and 3e - maximum strain ϵ^{max} - and 1e and 3c - minimum strain ϵ^{min} - compared with the far-field gauge 4S1, ϵ_{70}^{ff} . (b) Variation of the difference between maximum and minimum strain at each strip with increasing crack length.

residual and strains at 70 kN load appear to saturate. Fig. 9b) shows that the parameter $(\epsilon^{\max} - \epsilon^{\min})/\epsilon_{70}^{\text{ff}}$ appears to be extremely sensitive to crack growth - especially for the residual strain case. For example, consider the parameter for residual strains at strip 1, i.e. $(\epsilon_0^{\max} - \epsilon_0^{\min})/\epsilon_{70}^{\text{ff}}$, the variation this parameter is about 150% for a change in crack length of 20 mm whereas the parameter, $(\epsilon_{70}^{\max} - \epsilon_{70}^{\min})/\epsilon_{70}^{\text{ff}}$, varies by only 80%.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper describes a study on surface strains on the patch, of a patched cracked metallic specimen, in order to detect and monitor fatigue cracks in the metallic component. The specimen was subjected to constant amplitude tension-dominated cyclic loading and crack lengths, using eddy-current NDI, and surface strain measurements were monitored with increasing number of load cycles. The full field surface stresses were also determined by using the FAST thermoelastic technique. The following conclusions can be made from the study:

1. Surface strains on the patch, due to an applied in-plane load, show distinctive regions of low strains, over the crack, and high strains, above and below the crack. These results were observed by the strain surveys and by the FAST thermoelastic analysis. The surface strains over the crack, and above and below the crack appeared to be varying quite noticeably with increasing crack length.
2. Similar distributions around the crack were observed for surface residual strains as for strains taken under load. Also, surface residual strains appeared to be extremely sensitive to changes in crack length.
3. Surface strains around the crack region appear to vary linearly with crack length. However strains taken from sensors that were greater than 30 mm downstream from the crack tip appeared to show signs of saturation, and did not change with increasing crack length.
4. The crack appeared to show a region of influence which extended to about 10-15 mm above and below the crack and about 7-8 mm ahead of the crack. However the extent of these regions are specimen dependent and will depend on the stiffness of the adherent, adherends and the honeycomb core.
5. These results indicate that monitoring surface strains, and residual surface strains, appear to be a promising technique for detecting and monitoring crack growth beneath composite patches.

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